

Social Welfare, Development and Empowerment: Fields, Perspectives and Paradigms in Social Work Research in Mizoram

KALPANA SARATHY

Department of Socialwork, Mizoram University, Aizawl, Mizoram

EASWARAN KANAGARAJ

Department of Socialwork, Mizoram University, Aizawl, Mizoram

CHINNATHAMBI DEVENDIRAN

Department of Socialwork, Mizoram University, Aizawl, Mizoram

The present paper attempts a critical review of research conducted in various fields of social work by the department of social work, Mizoram University, over a period of five years (2004-2008). Social work research is an applied branch of methodology of social scientific research which is supposed to enhance the scope and effectiveness of social work practice in varied fields. This paper is aimed towards presenting a review of substantive, theoretical and methodological aspects of social work research conducted in Mizoram in the fields of welfare of the family, child, women, youth and the elderly; health and mental health; as well as rural, urban and tribal community development. From the overview of the studies conducted in the varied fields of Social Work in Mizoram, coexistence of the paradigms of social welfare, development and empowerment was observed. Methodologically speaking, the studies in all the fields of Social Work practice were predominantly quantitative in their orientation. Yet, mixed designs were used whereby qualitative methods as well as participatory methods were incorporated along with field survey in many of the studies.

Introduction

The present paper attempts a critical review of research conducted in various fields of social work by the department of social work, Mizoram University, over a period of five years (2004-2008). It presents a review of the theoretical, conceptual and methodological aspects of the research work done, their patterns and trends.

Social Work is a professional service based upon scientific knowledge and skill in human relations, which assists individuals alone or in groups, to obtain social and personal satisfaction and

independence. It is usually performed by a social agency or related organization (Friedlander, 1955). Historically, the goal of professional social work has been to enhance human well-being. It operates within the three paradigms of welfare, development and empowerment to achieve its ultimate goal of human welfare. The welfare paradigm emphasizes external support to the individuals to cope with their problems; while in the development paradigm self-reliance is emphasized. On the other hand, in the empowerment paradigm the peoples' involvement in determining the decisions that affect their lives are

emphasized.

The paper is presented in six sections. The context of the social work education and research is described in the first section. The second section is devoted to review the studies in the field of welfare of family, child, youth and elderly. The studies on health and mental health are reviewed in the third section. In the fourth section a review of the studies on women is attempted. The fifth section presents an overview of the research on tribal community development. In the concluding section the challenges and directions for future research are presented.

Research in Social Work

Social Work Research is often considered as one of the minor methods of social work practice (Friedlander, 1955). By considering only the scope of the research or the substantive issues concerned, social work research cannot be treated as one of the methods of social work profession. Though social work research shares the methodological orientations of social scientific research, it has no unique method or technique of research of its own. As Ramachandran and Nayak (1968) rightly observed, social work research is not as such a method of social work, but an applied branch of methodology of social scientific research. Social work research is the use of scientific methods in the search for knowledge, including knowledge of alternate practice and intervention techniques which would be of direct use to the social work profession and thus enhance the practice of social work method. It can be considered as a species of social scientific research (Ramachandran and

Nayak, 1968).

Research is a vehicle of development and advancement of any scientific discipline. Social work as applied social science and human service profession is no exception. Social work research reviews the existing laws, theories, concepts, methods and techniques for their relevance, adequacy and sufficiency from time to time. It widens the profession's horizons, refines its approaches, strategies, methods and techniques and aids to cope with the changing needs of society.

Social Work Education and Research Training in Mizoram

The department of social work was established in 1992 at the Aizawl campus of the North Eastern Hill University (NEHU). However, it is the formation of a full-fledged Central University at Aizawl that saw the department being operationalised. The department began offering post-graduate courses from 2002. Within 4 years, the first doctoral scholars were registered in 2006. Thereafter M. Phil. courses have begun in 2008. The department offers MSW, M.Phil and Ph.D. As research skills are necessary for practice of social work in different settings, training students in the application of quantitative, qualitative and participatory methods begin at postgraduate level. A separate course on social work research is a part of the MSW course. The course introduces the scientific method, its components, as well as methods of data collection, processing and analysis. It also provides an exposure to statistical testing. As a part of the curriculum, students undergo a ten days rural camp, wherein they

practice research methods in profiling the village community and assessing the community needs. Before the commencement of rural camp a one-day workshop on field survey and participatory rural appraisal is conducted for the students. These MSW students use their research methods in field work in the community settings in the third and fourth semesters. During the period 2002 -2007, the MSW curriculum has a dissertation component in the fourth semester. To integrate research and social work practice, research projects have been integrated with fieldwork in the fourth semester. In the M.Phil programme, advanced training in the philosophical foundations of social work is provided. The students are taught the applications of qualitative, quantitative and participatory methods. Practical exposure is sought to be provided via field practicum.

Despite having only a strength of 2-3 faculty members for over five years, the department has been able to produce over 80-dissertation/project work, which are essentially empirical studies on a range of social work concerns. Against this backdrop, the present paper restricts its scope to the studies conducted by MSW students. These studies have been on samples ranging between 30-120 persons. The next section presents a review of studies on welfare of family, children, youth and the elderly.

Family Life Cycle: Children, Youth and Elderly

Family is one of the basic institutions of our society. It plays a significant role in upbringing children as well as moulding the personality of an individual. Family members carry out

their functions and roles in the context of the family life cycle. The family life cycle is an ever-changing process which encapsulates marriage, procreation and raising of children, the departure of children from the household, retirement and death. At present, families are facing lots of challenges due to poverty, illiteracy, alcoholism and other related issues in Mizoram.

In view of these challenges, in the department some of the familial issues were studied in the context of Mizoram. The key challenges studied were marital breakdown (Fabawl, 2004), single parenthood (Lalhlimpui, 2006), and Mizo customary law (Lalmuanpuii, 2006). Fabawl (2004) assessed the impact of marital breakdown on family strength. Lalhlimpui (2006) attempted to identify the major challenges to single parent families in Aizawl while Lalmuanpuii (2006) assessed the perceptions on the challenges of Mizo Customary Law to women in matters of marriage, divorce and inheritance.

Children are the backbone and future of every nation. In India alone, children constitute about 40 percent of the total population. They are invaluable assets of any society and have a significant role to play in the development of our country. The future of any country depends on the holistic development of the children. They are facing numerous challenges such as child labour, child abuse, child marriage, children in conflict with the law, child prostitution, child beggary, and child trafficking. They are also deprived of proper food, clothing, shelter, parental care and education. They are in need of care and protection from the challenges and provision of love and protection and

meeting of emotional needs. The empirical studies were concerned with specific group of children in need of care and protection in the context of Mizoram.

There were studies on children of poor families (Lalramngheta, 2007), child labour (Lalhriatpuii, 2006), child abuse (Zorinpuii, 2007), children in conflict, (Lalrinchanna, 2006), girl children (Laltanpuii, 2006), adolescence, (Lalbiaksangi, 2007), and school children (Buli, 2004). These studies attempted a situational analysis of these specific groups of children and identified the major challenges faced by them from a social work perspective. All these studies presented demographic profile, socio-economic and psychosocial factors, the magnitude of the issues and challenges faced by the children in need of care and protection and children in conflict with the law. In addition, these studies suggested how social work methods and techniques can contribute in the governmental and nongovernmental settings to protect and promote the children.

Youth are an important section of our country as one third of our population comprises of youth. They are representing the nation's strength in terms of human resources. It is very important to take care and guide our young generation. If they are guided properly, they can become a great asset for our country. At present, they are facing lots of challenges due to poverty, unemployment, corruption, ethnic conflict. These problems ultimately collapse the personality of youth and they indulge in smoking, alcoholism, drug addiction, and face threat of HIV/AIDS infection, especially in the

northeast context.

Generally, the challenges of youth are related to the youth culture and lifestyle. In fact the studies in the department focused on culture and lifestyle of the youth. The study by Darrothanga (2007) on youth culture among college students focused on the beliefs and values as well as recreational patterns. As regards the lifestyle, a couple of studies were attempted in Mizoram. Mass media exposure (Lalniehkima, 2005), and recreational patterns (Hmingthanawii, 2006) of the Mizo youth was studied by some. One of the challenges of youth embedded in their life style in Mizoram is premarital sex. There was one study on premarital sex and quality of life (Lalringhetti, 2004). A closely related issue is HIV/AIDS. Youth awareness on HIV/AIDS among the youth was explored in one study (Lalhluipua, 2005).

These studies provide an insight into the youth culture in northeast India (Devendiran, 2008). They also give a picture of the challenges faced by youth due to the consumerist culture, and mass media exposure and how they are shaping the attitude of the youth. Moreover, these studies highlighted the quality of life and the lifestyle of youth in northeast India. The youth studies demonstrate the scope of working with young people for their development.

The most important life cycle of family is old age, which is an inevitable process of any human being. There are a few studies related to elderly persons. One is in the rural context which assessed the quality of life of rural elderly in Mizoram (Lalmuanpuii, 2004); and another study focused on the needs and problems of the urban elderly

(Lalrohluua, 2007).

Social work research in the fields of family, child, youth and the elderly focus mainly on the quality of life and needs and problems of specific groups. These studies used functional-structural and systems theory predominantly. It also emphasized the need for practicing social work in Mizoram and underlined the scope for application of the generalist social work approach as well as strengths and empowering perspectives at micro and macro levels. These studies were oriented towards social policy and social work practice in governmental and non-governmental contexts. These studies by and large were based on field survey while in some instances, case studies were also incorporated.

Health, Mental Health and Disability

Social work in healthcare was one of the first fields of professional practice to be established and remains one of the largest sectors of the profession in most of the developed countries (Dworkin, 1997; Hopps and Collins, 1995). In India, the specialized area of work in health has been offered since the 1930's. In Mizoram, this specialized area of work in health was offered to one batch of social work students.

The research work by way of dissertations in partial fulfillment of Post Graduate degree in the area of health has been predominantly in the area of reproductive and child health (RCH). In addition to this, they have been on issues related to HIV/AIDS as well as lifestyle illnesses such as diabetes (Hnamte, 2005) and cancer (Lalhlupuii, 2005). Spousal loss due to cancer and the attendant psychosocial challenges have

been explored in one study (Lalhlupuii, 2005); and this study employs the bio-psycho-social nature of exploration. Mental health concerns reflected in dissertations by students include studies related to stress as well as suicide and the psychosocial factors associated with its aetiology (Hauhnar, 2005). In both the studies, emphasis has been on social support and its perceived availability to persons with various health problems. Stress among student population, perceived stressors as well as social support and coping mechanisms by students in handling stress have been studied (Nag, 2005). The only study to be conducted in the area of disability has emphasized a family systems approach and explores the family environment and social support available to persons who are physically challenged (Lalrempuii, 2004).

Reproductive health issues concerning women's health are an important area of intervention for health social workers. Women's personal and social identities are more likely to be defined in terms of their biological capacity to conceive and carry a pregnancy and women are more likely than men to be held responsible for a couple's failure to conceive a child (Blyth, 2008).

In the department of social work, the studies in this area employ and reflect a Life Span approach. Further, these studies are located within the psychosocial and /or ecosystems theoretical paradigm of understanding. The studies on reproductive health in our department have therefore concentrated on meaning, perception and understanding by women to events within their reproductive life cycles. The significance of life events such as

menopause, often perceived as a negative event (and cessation of sexual functioning and an alteration in the meaning attributed to femininity) in a tribal society in the northeast is therefore important in many ways. Perceived effect of menopause on appearance, self-confidence, social support as well as on sexual functioning explain how sexuality and reproduction in particular have assumed importance in the narratives of women (Lalparmawii, 2005). Similarly, the meanings attributed to menstruation, the perceptions of adolescent girls on the problems associated with it as well as their need for social support have been explored (Zonunpari 2005). Such studies are located within gender and health and they follow a trajectory of women's events and understand the reproductive issues within a larger and broader societal structure and context. Notions, perceptions and reflections assume the proportions of a deconstruction and reconstruction in a society where there are few systematic explorations of this nature.

In a similar vein and interestingly the use of birth control measures by Mizo women has also been studied and results indicate that a vast majority of the respondents are using such measures. The significance of such studies highlight the need to explore women's reproductive choices and exercise of control over their own bodies.

Crosscutting issues related to health, sexuality and sexual functioning have been explored in several other studies. The studies in the area of sexual and reproductive health reflect the major concerns in the state such as HIV/AIDS. Studies in this area of concern of sexual

health dealt with common health problems of sex workers (Vanlalzari, 2005) as well as on drug abuse and HIV/AIDS (Laltanpuii, 2004) as also on perceptions related to HIV/ AIDS among the youth (Lalhlupuiia, 2005).

Almost all the studies related to reproductive health have indicated the need for more services and programmes for women. The need for pre-marital counseling, workshops, gender sensitive education, and counseling have been suggested. Family Life education is seen as a major suggestion that has emanated from the studies in this area. These studies therefore can be seen as contributing concretely in providing service directions for social workers. Further, almost all the studies in this area of health offer suggestions based on integrated social work approach and employ the generalist perspective in this regard. Scope for further research in this area of RCH include studies on infertility, sex selection, child bearing and rearing. One study in the department has however explored the child rearing practices of Mizo women (Elizabeth, 2004).

The studies conducted thus far on RCH have been developmental in orientation but are yet to assume an orientation to empowerment. Studies focusing on societal structure and the location of reproductive issues within this structure and the dynamics thereof are yet to be explored. Studies conducted elsewhere have for example explored the role of social work in challenging reproductive health disadvantage and inequality, locally, nationally and internationally, highlighting both constraints and suggestions for developing interventions (Blyth, 2008).

Three studies have focused on alcohol and its use in Mizo society. One has studied alcohol as a community problem (Lalnuntluangi, 2004) and has basically used a psychosocial approach while the others have focused on different target groups such as women (Lalmuanpuii 2008) and children (Lalengmawii 2008) in a community that is infamous in Mizoram for illicit trade and consumption of alcohol (rice beer). Both the studies have tried assessing the psychosocial needs and challenges of the target group concerned.

Security, Livelihood and Empowerment of Women

The issues concerning women have been explored using different paradigms and approaches. There have been but a few studies that have focused on women's issues. Some lie within the realm of women's health and security. A bio-psycho-social approach has been used to understand the very sensitive nature of domestic violence perpetrated against women.

The ability of social workers to detect and address domestic violence is critical given the prevalence and consequences of violence, the reluctance of women to identify abuse as a primary problem, and the multiple service needs of battered women and their children (Danis, 2003). Most social workers were not trained to deal with, or sensitive to the problem of domestic abuse (Kanuha, 1998), and despite social workers' extensive involvement in child and family services, mental health, and child welfare, the profession as a whole has been mostly silent about the problem. Battered women themselves have not had much good to say about their interactions with

social workers. They have reported that professionals often put them in a double bind by blaming them for either not wanting to stay and solve problems in their marriages or remaining in their abusive marriages without having personal or community resources to help them leave (Flynn, 1977).

In the department, one study has explored the issue of domestic violence and has predominantly employed qualitative means to collect and analyse data. The study has explored the mental health of women who are subjected to violence within their homes (Lalchhantluanga, 2006). In the context of Mizoram, this study has revealed that alcohol consumption by men and subsequent violence are major problems and the former is seen as being responsible for the latter. Emphasis in this study has been on the challenges faced by battered women. Social Work research has to lead towards practice and interventions. This study has highlighted that there are no transitional homes and facilities that are present for women as tertiary care facilities. In the absence of these facilities and following violence, women are compelled to compromise on residential circumstances in the homes of relatives, thereby compromising on the dignity of their existence. The study in question has certainly been cognizant of feminist research while its own location is still within the psychosocial one. The need to understand, analyse and criticize social structures that help perpetrate violence is a future direction of study and exploration for studies that are to understand violence.

Three studies have focused on livelihoods of women. One has had to

do with the sale of second-hand clothes by women in Aizawl (Liansangpuii, 2005). The second one deals with domestic workers (Ruth, 2007) while a third explores responses of women as heads in single-parent families (Lalhlimpuii, 2006). The studies highlight the role of women as income earners who eke their livelihoods placing themselves thus in double or multiple burdensome positions. They are exposed to risks and uncertainty both within and outside the home. The studies are placed within a paradigm that are welfarist and are psychosocial in their orientation.

There are a few studies focused on empowerment of women. This study explores the bearing of women's education, employment and social and political participation on women empowerment. This study attempted to conceptualize empowerment as women's involvement in household decision making in personal, domestic, social, economic and political domains (Zate, 2005). This study also attempted to identify the major constraints of women development and empowerment and downplayed the role of Mizo patriarchy in disempowering women. Another study on perceptions related to women's empowerment (Hmingthanpari 2007) basically documents how women and men in Mizoram view empowerment.

Community Development in Tribal Context

Community development is one of the fields of social work in India. Community development in this context aims at promoting socio economic development of the people by mobilizing and organizing them in the rural and urban community contexts. Here, a

typical social worker is engaged in grappling with four interrelated dimensions of the process of community development. They are the challenges; agencies service users (clientele) and strategies. The studies conducted in the department of social work addresses all these dimensions except the service users within a social development paradigm. Mizoram is predominantly a tribal state and undergoing the process of rapid urbanization. The Mizo rural and urban communities have been riddled with a number of problems in spite of their formalized social structure. Community development primarily is concerned with addressing these issues or challenges. Hence, a number of studies have been conducted. The studies mainly focused on three interrelated areas, viz., the challenges, institutions and strategies of community development.

Social work intervention requires a comprehensive, systematic and scientific understanding of the problems, issues or needs of rural and urban communities. In fact, the primary task of social workers is to identify these challenges and probe deeper into it. In Mizoram, in both rural and urban contexts, poverty and livelihood constitute the major challenge to community development and social work. The studies by Laltlanmawi (2004) and Malsawmdawngliani (2007) probed into the socio economic structural bases and dynamics of rural and urban poverty respectively. Both these studies traced the socio economic structural bases and bearing of livelihood on poverty. They also assessed the manifestations and causes of poverty from the poor and non-poor households. Further, they attempted to

understand the dynamics of poverty with the help of case studies from the lived experiences of the poor. One more aspect of poverty, which was probed in the urban study, was the role of state and civil society institutions in addressing the same.

The social work researchers not only probed into poverty but also other livelihood issues in both urban and rural communities. Zaitinvawra (2004) explored the patterns of transformation in rural livelihood in the wake of the switch over from shifting cultivation to settled agriculture in the rural context. Lalrinhlua (2006) studied agricultural marketing which is an issue closely related to agricultural livelihood in rural Mizoram. Zaitinvawra (2004) tried to assess the variations in the patterns of livelihood of shifting cultivators and semi settled agriculturists. He also probed into the willingness of the cultivators to permanent agriculture and the problems involved as well as their perceptions them. Lalrinhlua (2006) assessed the cultivators' access to agricultural marketing information infrastructure, and probed into the alternative channels and problems therein. In the urban context, Lalpekmawia (2006) studied the push and pull factors in migration of rural households to urban areas of Aizawl and the impact of the same on the livelihood and living conditions of the migrants. He also attempted to identify the major problems that daunt the migrants in the capital city of Mizoram.

There are some who studied peculiar problems of urbanization in Mizoram. The challenges to urban environment such as air pollution and solid waste management were probed by some

studies. Lalhruaitluanga (2006) assessed the pattern of domestic solid waste, its storage and disposal, and satisfaction over solid waste management in Aizawl. He also identified the major problems in the urban solid waste management in the popular perception. On the other hand, Lalengzuala (2007) attempted to understand the peoples' perceptions on air pollution as a social problem in Aizawl. He also tried to identify causes of air pollution, and assess the morbidity due to air pollution in the city. In the urban context, alcoholism as a community problem was explored by Lalnuntluangi (2004).

Today, inadequate supply of drinking water constitutes a major problem in both rural and urban communities in Mizoram. Lalrosangi (2005) attempted to study household drinking water management in a village community. She explored into the sources, distance traveled for collection, pattern of storage, use, and perceived adequacy of water.

The second dimension of the research are the agencies or institutions. State and civil society actors play a vital role in addressing the challenges and achieving the goals of improving the quality of life and social justice in rural and urban community contexts. The studies focus on the effectiveness of government programmes and various components of civil society in both contexts. Only one study has probed into the effectiveness of rural housing schemes (see Zothanpuui 2005). Some studies have probed into the role of local self-governing institutions in the rural development. Gangte (2007) explored the role of Kuki traditional institution

of chieftainship in tribal development in Manipur while Lalremtlunga (2007) assessed performance of village council in Mizoram. Role of voluntary organisations (Abraham, 2004) and self-help groups (Lalrinliana, 2004) in rural development have also been assessed. In the urban context, a few studies focus on the role of the major community organisations in community development (Hmar, 2008). There was a comparative study of leadership and community power structure and their role in community development also (Zonunkima, 2006).

The third dimension of the social work research in community development is that of strategies. There are various strategies followed at the community level to further the goals of social policy and social work by the state and civil society institutions. The studies have attempted to assess the status and relevance of the strategies of urban interaction (Lalthanzuali, 2005) and social mobilization (Kanagaraj and Ralte: 2007) in the rural context. In the urban context, the strategies followed by the state and civil society actors such as social development (Sailo, 2007), social action (Chawngthu, 2007), networking and collaboration (Lalmangaizuala, 2007), and poverty alleviation were assessed by their studies for their effectiveness in addressing the challenges of community development in Mizoram. Interestingly, one study attempted to assess the relationship between social capital, local governance and community development in both the rural and urban contexts (Lalramhluna, 2007).

Social work research on community development in both rural and urban

contexts adheres to social development paradigm while considering the challenges, and strategies. The livelihood challenges of the community especially poverty have gained the attention of the researchers. The focus of the studies on social mobilization, networking and collaboration, social development as well as social capital do demonstrate the developmental thrust of social work research in Mizoram. Considering the theoretical perspectives used in these studies, they are by and large interdisciplinary in nature. To be specific, these studies apply sociological, economic and political perspectives such as social capital, power structure, social mobilization to study the macro level factors and their bearing on development. The structural bases and dynamics were the two dimensions of probe in most of the studies and hence these studies provide systematic information on the structure of rural and urban communities and the dynamics of their working as well as problems. In fact, in all of these applied social science studies, there were a number of suggestions offered for macro level interventions by state civil society institutions and social work.

Methodologically, the question is whether the studies are quantitative or qualitative in nature. In fact, most of these studies were quantitative in their orientation. They use scales for measuring concepts and parametric and non-parametric statistics for assessing the relationship between them. They have attempted to study one or two communities and stratified random sampling procedure has been used. By and large they relied on field survey with structured interview schedule for data

collection. Simple statistical measures such as ratios, averages and percentages were used. Cross tabulation and bivariate statistics such as correlation were used to draw inferences. They have not used any multivariate techniques for analysis.

Yet, the tendency is to use qualitative information in terms of case studies so as to understand the dynamics of community development in rural and urban contexts. For instance, the studies on the challenge of poverty in rural (Laltlantlanmawi, 2004) and urban contexts (Malsawmdawngliani, 2007) used case studies to describe the process of impoverishment. To discuss the role of state and civil society actors in implementation of housing schemes (Zothanpuii, 2005) and the role of community leadership in community development (Zonunkima, 2006) case studies were used. In the studies on strategies of urban poverty alleviation (Dawnkimi, 2008), networking and collaboration, (Lalmangaihza, 2006) case studies were explored to understand their working. One more emerging trend is use of participatory methods. In the more recent studies on poverty (Malsawmdawngliani 2007; Dawnkimi 2008), and community organisations, relational methods of participatory learning and action have been used along with quantitative and qualitative methods.

Conceptualization and operationalisation are the key aspects of research, which need our attention as sophistication in it could also contribute to advancement of social science. Though these studies were focusing on the macro level reality and addressing the issues concerned with the institutional aspects of human social

problems, they have used cognitive behavioural approach for conceptualization and measurement of constructs. In a few studies social network conceptualization are also applied. Interestingly, most of the concepts were operationalised in terms of their multiple dimensions. Behavioural constructs such as member participation in SHG (Lalrinliana 2004) use of tools and techniques (Zaitinvawra, 2005), water use (Lalrosangi, 2005), etc. were operationalised in terms of four point scales. Cognitive constructs such as perception and satisfaction were used in a number of studies. For instance, cognitive constructs such as perceived standard of living, perceived manifestations, perceived causes of poverty (Laltlanmawi, 2005; Malsawmdawngliani, 2007), satisfaction over housing schemes (Zothanpuii, 2005), perceived impact of SHGs (Kanagaraj and Ralte 2009) etc., were measured in terms of four point scales with a number of items. Interestingly, in conceptualization and operationalisation of social capital, both the cognitive and behavioural aspects were combined. In conceptualizing community power structure (Zonunkima 2006), interorganisational collaboration in social welfare (Ralte and Kanagaraj 2007), as well as interaction pattern of SHGs with other organisations (Kanagaraj and Ralte) social network concepts and diagrammatic representations were used.

It is noteworthy that the social work curriculum (MSW) has influenced the choice of research topics and these research works are often used as reference material in classroom teaching as well as providing supervisory input

to field work practice. The study of community power structure (Zonunkima, 2006) is while teaching the course on community practice. The studies on rural and urban poverty by Laltnanmawi (2005), Malsawmdawnglini (2007), and Dawnkimi (2008) are used as reference material in teaching the courses on rural and urban development (MSW 304) as well as tribal development (MSW 404). The study on shifting cultivation (Zaitinvawra and Kanagaraj) is used teaching students on tribal problems (MSW 404).

Concluding Observations

Professional social work ultimately aims at enhancing human well-being at multiple levels. Social work research aims at enhancing the appropriateness and effectiveness of social work intervention with individuals, families, groups, communities, organisations, etc. The coexistence of the paradigms of social welfare, development and empowerment could be observed. Among them the predominance of developmental paradigm could be observed in the fields of youth, women, health and community development while the welfare paradigm dominates the research on family and children. Empowerment gains currency in the fields of women, youth, and community development. In the tribal context of Mizoram, social work research was conducted in the fields of family, child, youth and elderly, women, health and community development. The challenges to social practice were focused in all these fields while target groups were focused in the field of child welfare. The role of institutions and strategies were focused only in the field of community

development.

Methodologically speaking the studies in all the fields of social work practice were quantitative in their orientation. Yet, mixed designs were used whereby qualitative methods as well as participatory methods were incorporated along with field survey in many studies in different fields especially women, health and mental health and community development. There is thus a move towards a multimodal approach rather than methodological pluralism or shift from quantitative to qualitative paradigm.

All the above discussions thus prove that in a short period of five years, social work research in Mizoram had generated literature for teaching the courses on the methods and fields of social work. In this endeavor they have addressed the core issues of social work practice. Further, they have generated national publications too. It is noteworthy to mention here that during this five-year period the department was functioning in the city and did not have access to UGC inflibnet and high quality international research journals at all.

The major limitation of Social Work research in Mizoram is that most of them were conducted in and around Aizawl city. Considering the socio economic diversity of the North East their conclusions may have limited generality. Yet, they certainly show the directions for further research. The challenges to social work research in Mizoram are: (i) integration of social work theory, practice and research, (ii) testing social work models and approaches with field experiments, (iv) formulating and testing indigenous theories (v) deepening the understanding through the application

of qualitative and participatory methods, (vi) documentation and publications of studies in national and international journals. These remain to be co-opted within the vast paradigm of social work research which is continuing to grow.

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Corresponding Author

Easwaran Kanagaraj, Associate Professor, Mizoram University, Aizawl - 796 004. Mizoram.
Email: mekanagaraj@gmail.com